

The ‘alpha’ parameter for quantifying non-single-exponential photoluminescence decays

This short note summarizes the origin and definition of the dimensionless alpha parameter, denoted as α , which can be used to quantify the non-single-exponential character of photoluminescence decay curves, measured for different materials. The main purpose of this note is to increase the visibility and practical use of the alpha parameter among researchers working with non-single-exponential photoluminescence decays.

Non-single-exponential photoluminescence (PL) decays, also referred to in different contexts as luminescence decays, fluorescence decays, emission decays, or time-resolved photoluminescence decays, are commonly observed in many classes of luminescent materials, including colloidal quantum dots, semiconductor nanostructures, phosphors, and disordered or heterogeneous emitter ensembles. A quantitative assessment of the degree of non-single-exponentiality is often needed when comparing PL decay curves measured for different samples, emission wavelengths, or experimental conditions. A commonly used way to quantify non-single-exponential decay is to fit the decay curve with a stretched-exponential, or Kohlrausch-type, function,

$$I_{PL}(t) = I_0 \exp \left[- \left(\frac{t}{\tau} \right)^\beta \right]$$

where the stretching exponent β describes the deviation from a single-exponential decay. This approach is widely used in the analysis of

luminescence and photoluminescence decays.^{1,2} However, β is meaningful only within the stretched-exponential model and therefore characterizes one specific functional form of non-single-exponential decay, rather than providing a general descriptor applicable to arbitrary PL decay shapes. This limitation is avoided by the alpha parameter, which describes the shape of a PL decay curve in a model-independent way and does not require assuming a particular analytical form of the decay.

The conceptual motivation for the parameter α appeared in the 2020 paper by Zatoryb and Klak,³ where two different average lifetime formulas for non-single-exponential PL decays were analyzed and discussed. In that work, it was shown that the following two average quantities:

$$\langle \tau_1 \rangle = \int_0^\infty \frac{I_{PL}(t)}{I_{PL}(0)} dt$$

and

$$\langle \tau_2 \rangle = \frac{\int_0^\infty t I_{PL}(t) dt}{\int_0^\infty I_{PL}(t) dt}$$

are the same only for a single-exponential PL decay. In the above equations, $I_{PL}(t)$ denotes the measured PL decay curve, and $I_{PL}(0)$ denotes the PL decay intensity at time $t = 0$. For non-single-exponential PL decays, $\langle\tau_1\rangle$ and $\langle\tau_2\rangle$ generally differ, with $\langle\tau_2\rangle > \langle\tau_1\rangle$ for a monotonically decreasing non-single-exponential PL decay. As suggested by Zatoryb and Klak,³ the difference between $\langle\tau_1\rangle$ and $\langle\tau_2\rangle$ can be used as a basis to assess how strongly a PL decay curve deviates from a single-exponential function.

The alpha parameter was later explicitly defined and applied in the 2023 paper by Zatoryb et al.⁴ as

$$\alpha = \langle\tau_1\rangle/\langle\tau_2\rangle$$

For an ideal single-exponential PL decay,

$$\alpha = 1$$

For non-single-exponential PL decays,

$$0 < \alpha < 1$$

Thus, lower values of α correspond to a stronger deviation from single-exponential decay. In this sense, α provides a compact, dimensionless measure of the non-single-exponential character of a PL decay curve. In the 2023 study,⁴ this parameter was used to analyze spectrally resolved PL decay dynamics of thick-shell CdSe/CdS colloidal quantum dots and to

visualize emission-energy-dependent changes in PL decay shapes in the context of energy transfer between quantum dots.

The alpha parameter can be useful whenever PL decay curves are not well described by a single-exponential function and a compact, model-independent measure of their shape is needed. It allows different PL decays to be compared using a single dimensionless number, complementary to the average lifetime. In particular, it can help identify changes in decay kinetics caused by processes such as energy transfer, trap-assisted recombination, sample heterogeneity, or a broad distribution of decay rates.

It should be noted that $\langle\tau_1\rangle$ and $\langle\tau_2\rangle$ are often calculated using alternative expressions to avoid direct numerical integration of the PL decay curve. This can be done, e.g., by fitting the PL decay with a multi-exponential function of the form:

$$I_{PL}(t) = \sum_{i=1}^{i=n} A_i \exp\left[-\frac{t}{\tau_i}\right]$$

and calculating $\langle\tau_1\rangle$ and $\langle\tau_2\rangle$ as:

$$\langle\tau_1\rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} A_i \tau_i}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} A_i} \quad \text{and} \quad \langle\tau_2\rangle = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} A_i \tau_i^2}{\sum_{i=1}^{i=n} A_i \tau_i}$$

where A_i and τ_i are the amplitude and lifetime, respectively, and n denotes the number of exponents used in the fit.

Figure 1. Comparison of the stretching exponent β and the alpha parameter α for simulated stretched-exponential PL decay curves. As β decreases, the decay becomes increasingly non-single-exponential, which is reflected by the corresponding decrease in α .

Researchers who find the parameter α useful for the analysis of non-single-exponential PL decays are encouraged to cite Ref. 4, where α was explicitly defined and applied.

References

- (1) J. R. Martins et al., “*Statistical Analysis of Photoluminescence Decay Kinetics in Semiconductor Nanocrystals*”, *The Journal of Physical Chemistry C* 126, 20745–20753 (2022).
- (2) R. Chen, “*Apparent stretched-exponential luminescence decay in crystalline solids*”, *Journal of Luminescence* 102–103, 510–518 (2003).
- (3) G. Zatoryb and M. M. Klak, “*On the choice of proper average lifetime formula for an ensemble of emitters showing non-single exponential photoluminescence decay*”, *Journal of Physics: Condensed Matter* 32, 415902 (2020). **DOI:** 10.1088/1361-648X/ab9bcc
- (4) G. Zatoryb, A. Adamski, M. Chrzanowski, M. Bański, A. M. Żak, and A. Podhorodecki, “*Spectrally Resolved Kinetics of Energy Transfer Within a Single Emission Band of Highly Luminescent Thick-Shell CdSe/CdS Colloidal Quantum Dots*”, *Physica Status Solidi (b)* 260, 2200416 (2023). **DOI:** 10.1002/pssb.202200416